

Use Of Academic Networks And Their Impact On The Development Of Responsibility Towards Self-Learning Education Through The Web In The Teaching And Communication Techniques Of Students

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Abstract

The experiment proposed the usage of a global educational network called Edmodo, which is still an uncommon reality in many schools. The aim of the current research is to determine the impact of Edmodo academic networking on the development of responsibility towards self-learning education through the web in teaching and communication techniques, and the measure of responsibility towards self-learning education over the web, as well as the development of content in the techniques of education and communication. The results of the research resulted in statistically significant differences between the averages of the grades of individuals in the experimental group in the tribal and dimension standards of the measure of responsibility towards self-learning education through the web in favor of the remote application. The recommendations and proposals indicate the importance of research variables in conducting similar research, and the extent to which they benefit from their integration in the field of education.

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Introduction

Learning environment in the 21st century has extended beyond the walls of the traditional classroom setting as a result of technology permeating almost every sector in the society, especially the educational sector, hence the experiment proposed the usage of a global educational network called Edmodo, which is still an uncommon reality in many schools. The objective is to create a site in which the teacher and the students can share ideas, suggestions, post comments, as well as widen their knowledge of digital tools.

Social networking sites are one of the new and most popular communications technology items and have radically changed the way people and groups are linked and exchanged and shared information. The social networks have taken over the world and preoccupied the minds of people; the world has become a place without barriers in terms of information, as people can now express their opinions and also see the opinions of others at any time without barriers. Social networks have removed obstacles and difficulties and have become a platform for the silent majority, a channel of communication, and a powerful means of interaction between people (Clark and Berge, 2006). Social networking could become an integral component of the educational environment if implemented effectively.

Research published in the newspaper 'Emirates Today' on 28th April, 2012 stated that social networking sites are beginning to spread to classrooms, and many educators seek to use these media to achieve their educational goals. The activities of social networks allow the emphasis to be on analysis and the gathering of data and contact with experts; blogs can be used to promote productive debates and dialogues which can be beneficial when shared on electronic information sites. There are a number of recent important trends that have emerged in the educational process. It is important for educators to note such a pattern and to profit from it in a great way and also to benefit from applications that work within the purposes of academic communication, which has shown its active role through its integrated management systems. For integrated learning, Edmodo is the network of academic communication in the educational framework (Cheong, 2010).

Edmodo is a free social educational network that offers resources to teachers, students and schools in a convenient and easy way to connect, exchange ideas and share educational materials, so that teachers can build an on-site account and provide lessons for learners. The network is available on three types of accounts: The teacher's account, the learner's account, and the account of the guardian, and is used by both according to the need, and the quality of interest. The learner registers using the secret number provided by the teacher giving him access to the hypothetical class created by the teacher, where he can thus take part in the lessons and assignments (Evans, 2008).

Mustafa (2015) states that Edmodo is a free social learning network that provides teachers and students with a safe environment for communication and collaboration, sharing educational content and digital applications, as well as homework, grades and discussions; it combines the advantages of Facebook and Blackboard Learning Management Systems (LMS), using web technology '2.0'. It currently employs more than 70 million users worldwide and thus deserves the title of the world's first and largest social learning network. It is also possible to use the idea of flipped classroom in education as an instructional model, aimed at using digital technology and the Internet in a way that enables teachers to plan lessons through videos, audio files or other media, so that students can see at home or elsewhere using their laptops, smartphones, or tablets before attending the class (Fernandez et al., 2009).

The development in the field of information, networking and communication systems has led to a clear change in all areas, especially in the field of educational institutions, with the emergence of the term e-learning largely in education and training services, so these educational institutions have to change the building of their organizational structures. In light of the changes that have occurred, and in view of the rapid development of such modern technologies and their applications in the field of education to bring about a clear change for learners and the educational process in particular, there is need to shift from teacher-based learning to learner-based learning (Lan and Sie, 2010). This is why it was necessary to face the rapid and dramatic changes in technological progress, the information revolution and the rapid development of devices, programs and means of communication, and encourage students to provide all that is new in the field of teaching and communication technologies and discover and develop their talents highlighting them on different Levels within the classroom, encouraging them to compete externally and motivating them to attain the best levels. This requires them to put in more efforts and take more time to provide information that responds to the needs and interests of learners who focus on the growth and development of their personality and responsibility towards education giving him confidence in his ability to learn by himself. This ensures the continuity of learning and education throughout the life cycle with self-guidance in a healthy environment without threat from any direction and any kind.

The development of vocational technical education and training in the knowledge and information age requires the improvement and development of teaching methods and training techniques to coincide with the important development of information and communication technologies, as this development has opened up new horizons for the field of education and training in terms of available means. The new possibilities and techniques used and the educational contents are advanced and modern, but on the other hand, the correct exploitation of this development exposes the field of education and training to many challenges and stakes such as: illiteracy, quality, economic and strategy. Adel (2005) used modern information and communication technologies in the field of education and advanced technologies to increase the quality of the educational process and develop curricula and methods of teaching and technical and vocational education (Mohammed, 2004). There is urgent need to develop education systems by relying on modern technologies and applications in the field of internet, exchanging information to meet the future challenges and also applying them in the educational process.

Methodology

Instrument and procedures

The research problem was analyzed by conducting unregulated interviews with students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University to ascertain why they were unable to acquire the cognitive aspects and the performance skills in their responsibility towards self-learning education and educational techniques. The reasons were as follows: - Some students talked about individual differences between them but which were not considered during the theoretical and practical study. The teaching method adopted does not effectively affect the students participation in e-learning and the sense of self-learning towards the techniques of education and communication. This study was explained conducting a test on 60 students to measure students' responsibility towards self-learning education associated with the teaching and communication techniques. It was found that 80% of students did not have the self-responsibility to learn. From the above, it is evident that the students of Imam Abdul Rahman bin Faisal University lacked the ability to develop their sense of self-responsibility towards the direction of their learning of teaching and communication techniques. An important motivation of the researcher to use the academic network Edmodo, is that the method of learning and teaching was transferred to adapt to the innovations of the era based on smart, digital devices, electronic interaction, group learning, self-orientation, thinking skills, problem solving, and green learning by reducing the use of paper and optical discs in education and its residues. We find that the network helps to raise the abilities of learners and their level of awareness and develop the skill of cooperation, interaction and participation in ideas to solve problems, develop their performance and keep them updated in their field of study. It also attracts them to the educational process as participants and motivations with the teacher during the learning process and not just recipients. It is therefore important to work on recruiting Edmodo in education and preparing teachers to be able to deal with the latest developments in technology because of their important role in driving and developing learning.

Search problem

The problem of this research can be identified as 'poor level and low sense of self-responsibility in teaching and communication techniques, and through this research was done using modern methods and techniques by the researcher in raising the professional level, and performing the pattern of self-learning over the web. Through the Edmodo academic network, the problem of the current research can be formulated in the following main question: What is the impact of Edmodo academic network in developing responsibility towards web-based self-learning education among students of Imam Abdul University Rahman bin Faisal in the teaching and communication techniques and their attitudes towards them? The following sub-question is branched out from this question: How to set up the Edmodo academic network for students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University in teaching and communication techniques.

Research objectives

The current research aims to:

- 1) Know how to set up the academic network among students and faculty members in the Division of Education Technology in Education and Communication Technologies;
- 2) Identifying responsibility development skills towards self-learning education developed by students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University;
- 3) Know the impact of the academic network in the development of responsibility towards web-based self-learning education among students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University in teaching and communication techniques.

The importance of research

The importance of this research are as follows:

- 1) The current research contributes to the development of the skills of designing inverted learning classes through the Edmodo environment of students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University;
- 2) Overcoming the problems of education, which are represented by increasing the demand for education and the number of students without a great deal of self-responsibility towards what they learn;
- 3) Keeping up with modern educational and technological trends, which call for the need to benefit from academic networks and employ them in education;
- 4) Research may help encourage the employment of self-learning to support the learning process and develop their self-responsibility towards what they learn.

Research limits: The current research is limited to academic networks, responsibility for self-learning education through the web, teaching, and communication techniques. The research experience was actually applied in the 2018/19 academic year.

Sample research: Students from different departments of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University was selected randomly and used as research sample. A total of 60 students divided into (10) students as a survey sample, and 50 students in the experimental group.

Research methodology: In light of the nature of the research, the researcher used the experimental method to determine the impact of academic networks represented by the Edmodo network in the development of responsibility towards self-learning education, where the researcher applied the measure of responsibility towards education after conducting the experiment to individual sample. The researcher performed the statistical treatments necessary to measure the impact and comparison between both groups. Figure 1 shows the experimental research design.

Search terms

This include:

1. Edmodo: This is known procedurally as a social network dedicated to education, combining Facebook and Blackboard, using web technology 2.0 controlled by the teacher to communicate with learners through an open space where messages are sent and received with textual and audio discussions on their grades, tests, and duties etc. Using this platform, the teacher and the students can share ideas, suggestions, post comments, as well as widen their knowledge of digital tools.

E-learning has now become a very important education mode, and various E-learning systems and prototypes have been developed. In knowledge society, updates of knowledge is accelerating, continuing education and lifelong learning has accordingly emerged. As a solution to these new education forms, we proposed a novel E-learning mode, that is, web-based self-learning,

2. Web self-learning: This is the educational activity carried out by the learner driven willingly to develop his preparations, abilities in response to his inclinations and interest to achieve the development of his personality, integration, and successful interaction with the academic network Edmodo. In teaching and communication techniques, the learner take the initiative, with or without the assistance of others, in diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, and evaluating learning outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

Edmodo

There are several recent trends noticed by educators that have emerged in the educational sector at the moment, which are very important and have a profound impact on how students collaborate and learn in their world (Ahern et al., 2006). Teachers have noted that Edmodo strengthened the relationship between students, and led to a stronger classroom community. Hence, Edmodo can be seen as Learning Management System (LMS), which can facilitate teachers to set up and manage their online classes easily. Edmodo was founded in Chicago, Illinois, in 2008, and the idea came from Jeff O'Hara and Nick Borg, who worked in the technical support department of Chicago schools. They saw the extent to which students used social media sites, such as Facebook, Twitter, and others, and the way they communicated with others, especially outside the classroom, and noticed the interruption of that communication between students as soon as they entered the classroom, and launched an experience of co-operation between two adjoining educational institutions. In the form of a network of cooperation and social learning, the first social network for educational purposes was established to harmonize the school community with the student community outside the school, the Edmodo network, which aims to integrate education into the 21st century environment. After expanding to more than 85% of America's major schools, as well as many schools around the world, the network has shifted its headquarters to San Mateo, California.

The concept of the academic network Edmodo

Edmodo network is an application that supports ios devices, phone applications in addition to its application on the web. The Edmodo network enables teachers to share content, make a vote, distribute assignments, adding videos, making student groups, adding an event calendar and manage communication with students, colleagues, and parents. Edmodo is teacher-centric in its design and philosophy. Parents can access their accounts to see their children's grades and duties, and the teacher can communicate with students' parents and notify them of late duties and extracurricular activities through the app's website. The app is a social and educational means where the site connects more than 19 million teachers and students worldwide, and only requires registration on the site (Gewertz and Catherine, 2012: 6).

One of the objectives of the Edmodo educational network is to provide quality educational content for learners and facilitate communication between teachers, learners, and parents around the world to create a modern learning environment based on the latest modern technologies to attract the largest number of participants, as well as providing learners with the highest number of participants. A good level of education that they can see and return to at any time they ask questions and concerns and also register other virtual interdisciplinary classes to bring new learners from other countries to register. In general, three basic points that determine the true goal of Edmodo are: 1) help teachers in the use of social media to allocate the classroom for each individual student; 2) increase the horizon of learners and their thinking and abilities in education; 3) the existence of this program does not eliminate all problems, but makes difficult tasks easy on the network.

Edmodo is also a free and secure network that guarantees the safety and privacy of learners; it is a closed environment with no special information requested from the students, and use the Internet, and many websites to improve educational abilities, exchange experiences, and learn new methods in the e-learning profession. The site provides a simple way for teachers and students in a virtual class to connect and collaborate. Allah (2015) in his report stated that there are three main themes shared by the advantages, including features related to the teacher, learner, and parents and can sum up the advantages as follows: the possibility of the teacher contacting his students in the classroom and other students from other semesters, the teacher can evaluate the work. The teacher has full control and management, the teacher communicates with his colleagues at the same school or from outside the school to exchange materials and ideas, use applications, educational programs and different locations, safe and easy to use, a closed environment that no individual can access and violate the privacy of others other than allowed to do so, no special information is requested from students, students join the classes by invitation only from their teachers, allowing senior management officials to supervise the sub-domains, accessing Edmodo through smart phone applications or any browser through the link m.edmodo.com, the ease of contact of the teacher with the parents of students, and the ease of informing them as regard the level of their children is a way to communicate quickly in terms of time and space, have the property of archiving all messages, changing the pattern of teaching in the classroom and making it one of the 21st century classes that

relies on digital, interactive courses, social communication, increased interaction between students, the use of smart devices, the interaction of learners and their communication to solve problems. Shortening the time by putting a specific topic on the site (Post) and then discussing it with students, helps learners to complete their duties, especially students who are absent, where the duty on the site and the calendar helps to organize important ideas and appointments, expand the circle of learners and communication between them and the teacher., It also expand learners' knowledge by keeping up-to-date in their field, giving shy students an opportunity to share and publish their opinions, reduce spending in classrooms, reduce paper use and printing.

Lessons, which are often in the form of short educational videos or files (PDF) and (doc), are displayed for students to see when they log on the site, and these lessons can be attached to homework with tests specified by the professor and specific date set for completion. Students in answering these duties and tests are evaluated by the teacher individually so that students can see the marks and notes given to them by their teacher, .and the students can also send their inquiries and concerns through the service correspondence from their own account for the professor to answer later.

Web self-learning

From the early 1980s, self-learning theories and models began in efforts to explain what the learner should do to succeed in learning. Self-learning has several synonymous terms, including self-guided learning, and self-organized learning. Self-learning is defined as a way to encourage individuals to become self-educated, which is mainly based on self-reading programs (Boekaerts et al., 2000). Sarah (2005) introduced self-learning as the educational activity of the learner, driven by his own desire to develop his preparations and abilities in response to his dispositions and interests to achieve the development of his personality, integration, and interaction with his community. Self-learning is one of the most important learning methods that allows the employment of efficient learning skills, which contributes to the development of humans behaviorally, cognitively and emotionally, thus enabling him to absorb the data of the coming era, a pattern of learning that teaches students on how to learn what they want to. The acquisition and mastery of self-learning skills enables the individual to learn at all times and throughout life outside and within school, which is known as continuous education, and the importance of self-learning (Mohamed and Basiony, 2004; Csaplar, 2009, 2010).

The most striking difference from my experience between the Western teacher – in the United States of America, for example, and the Arab teacher is the decentralization of the learning and education process. Each state and province has its own goals and approaches that the people of the province have in common. It is also an important difference that the educational system focuses on social, psychological, and cognitive personality building, as well as the required academic achievement, if we take an example of the objectives of an American school that is sufficient to compare it with the objectives of any educational system in any Arab country. First, the objectives are based on the education of the child in all aspects as earlier mentioned where the focus is on building an integrated personality socially, psychologically, morally, and academically, although there is evidence of positive self-learning on the performance of the learner in education. Overall, the addition of internet technology is a positive or negative factor for self-learning among students, and for the most benefit, there are additional special criteria required for successful teaching and learning in online learning environments (Cavanaugh et al., 2004; Lynch, 2004).

Tools for self-learning and its applications through the web-based self-learning on the internet where the teacher is missing realistically, besides increasing the dependence and responsibility on the learner in achieving the goals and activities of learning adds difficulties to the learner, especially in students with low skills in self-reliance in learning, and this dictates the need to find educational learning tools based on internet technology (McLoughlin and Hollongworth, 2001). Web self-learning environments must be built on the needs of learners and compatibility with their abilities, goals and characteristics and education strategies characterized by enhanced motivation among the learners to assist them in self-learning (Cennamo and Ross, 2000); its success requires the availability of educational tools that combine internet technology on the one hand and self-learning activities on the other. Online-based educational tools include a wide variety of simultaneous and asynchronous communication tools, multimedia, and super-multimedia tools. Learning systems management tools promote educational interaction among learners, such as sharing and comparing information, and building meaningful knowledge (Hartely and Bendixen, 2001).

Educational internet tools support the learner in enhancing his skills. Dabbagh and Kistanas (2004) highlights the importance of this in the fact that the online learning environment requires the learner to achieve a high degree of competence and skill in self-learning to achieve learning goals (Kistanas and Chow, 2002). Dabbagh and Kistanas (2004) have classified the Internet's pedagogical tools in self-learning as follows: 1) Internet-based super media: the educational use of multimedia applications on browsers, and engines search, browse information, locate, download and save files, and evaluate the content of websites. Multimedia based on the Internet includes browser-based tools that enable the display of materials without HTML formats, such as fees, motion, display files, and files Pdf. Content composition and transmission includes HTML text editing software or web page writing programs, while collaboration and communication includes e-mail, discussion areas, news

groups, chat programs, audio and video conference tools, and document sharing tools (Niemi et al., 2003; Whipp and Chiarelli, 2004; Cennamo and Ross, 2000; Loomis, 2000; Cavanaugh et al., 2004; Clark, 2001; Heo and Joung, 2004).

A number of results that emerged from the value of self-learning through the web in the educational process, include: 1) That there is no real link between self-learning activities and online learning tools; 2) focusing attention on computers as a means of teaching in the classroom; 3) only to teach computer as a culture and the computer used as an educational material itself and not information technology; 4) As a tool for teaching and learning, - data scan also indicates the lack of virtual schools as in global trials. Self-learning skills have improved after using the management of the 'IQ Learn' system in the early-stage undergraduate students and students have succeeded in applying internet tools to self-learning, such as setting goals, organizing, scheduling tasks, taking notes, using charts, seeking help from teachers and peers, and self-monitoring. Students want the online learning site to include display of grades, goal lists, and test feeding. High self-confidence and self-regulation among learners as there has been a decrease in anxiety of the most efficient self-learning strategies reviewing notes, keeping records, self-evaluation promotes online self-learning, characterized by interface planning. The site is simple and consistent, emphasizing on the remoteness of social interaction in communication, and the assistance and technical and educational support.

Results

The experimental assumption of the study states that there are statistically significant differences at the level of $0.01 \geq \alpha$ between the average grades of students of the experimental group. In the dimension standards, - the measure of responsibility towards web-based self-learning is in favor of the remote application.

Table 1 shows the value of (T) 08.8, which is a function at level 01, is in favor of the experimental group after the application of the academic network Edmodo, indicating the achievement of the previous experimental imposition.

Table 2 shows the result of the magnitude of the impact of the independent variable using the Edmodo academic network on the second child variable 'in increasing responsibility towards self-learning. Table 2 also shows results of the $ETA^2\eta$ box and the calculation of the value of d. It is evident from Table 2 that the value $^2\eta$ of the '0.889' and the value of d (5.90) is greater than (0.8), indicating that the independent variable 'Edmodo Academic Network' has a high impact on the second dependent variable 'in increasing the level of self-learning' with a significant degree of impact.

Discussion

It is evident from the results of Table 1 that the value of (T) function at level 01, is in favor of the experimental group after the completion of the application of the academic network Edmodo, and the results of the current research in the study of the impact of the academic network Edmodo in the development of the level of participatory e-learning, and the responsibility of self-learning. Through the web, the students of Imam Abdul Rahman Bin Faisal University, and results of the study of Fatima (2007), Taradi et al. (2005), Kocoglu et al. (2010), Grosz (2012), Holmquist (2010), Alshwaier et al. (2012), and McCarthy (2010), and the results of the current research showed that the degree of the availability of innovations and techniques of teaching technology represented by the experimental treatment of the academic network Edmodo was low, and the general arithmetic average was 2.7.

There are high constraints in the use of teachers academic network Edmodo in teaching. The average general arithmetic to the degree of difficulties is 1.44, and despite the convergence of the mathematical averages of the two applications, the differences were in favor of the experimental group, considering the convergence of averages. Due to the conservation mechanism that the student is accustomed to with the traditional method, and the nature of the performance that requires a call of information, the results indicate the impact of the academic network Edmodo in the development of responsibility towards self-education through the web in the members of the experimental sample. Due to the simplification of the information provided by the teacher, their involvement in the education process, in addition to providing the learner with the opportunity to roam freely between the concepts of the subject regularly presented to their attention, the booklet of activities accompany the learner to write his notes while learning and guide him with what he sees, thus making him more positive while learning.

Conclusions, Implications and Recommendations

There is need to use some experts and specialists in the process of training in the use of educational innovations and techniques, and also need to train faculty members in different colleges, especially education technology, as some of them are basically skilled enough to use them in the educational process, which may make the teaching process an ineffective lecture. There is also need to equip schools with the capabilities that allow the employment of academic networks from the internet and high-efficiency devices, as well as the need to urge

students to participate in the connection of internet networks so that they can use the inverted classrooms during the academic network Edmodo.

In light of the above, the two former cases must be merged into one teaching position. This is achieved through the integration of new technologies and sites into the teaching process because of their great strength in integrating and engaging learners in the educational process turning them into active participants in learning and giving them a sense of responsibility in the formation of their sources of knowledge. The meeting is appropriate to connect and integrate the two former cases into integrated and interconnected parties, that is, it harmonize the academic and educational aspects, to achieve the desired objectives, expanding the use of self-learning programs in the teaching of different practical courses and improving the quality of education, through which the learner is responsible for what he learns. Together with other traditional learning activities, inverted learning classes through the Edmodo environment in student's lectures are an effective learning component in e- learning. Electronic Courses offered in e- Learning Management Systems such as "black board" across university site are also an integral part of the society knowledge and life-long learning for learners.

Important points to note:

- An increasing number of faculties and scientific departments uses academic networks as open learning resources;
- Academic networks can be offered for a larger segment of local and international universities;
- Those who use these networks will have great positive trends towards learning and using electronic communication in an excellent way;
- Edmodo academic networking lectures are an important service in e-learning;
- The current research contributes to the development of the skills of designing inverted learning classes through the Edmodo environment of students;
- The current research suggests a strong and highly significant correlation between the use of Edmodo academic networking by learners and their performance in the teaching and communication techniques;
- Overcoming the problems of education, which are represented by the increasing demand for education and the increasing number of students without a great deal of self-responsibility towards what they learn;
- Keeping up with modern educational and technological trends, which call for the need to benefit from academic networks and employ them in education;
- This research may help encourage the employment of self-learning to support the learning process and develop their self-responsibility towards what they learn.

Conflict of interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest.

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